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CHARACTERIZATION OF CARBON-FIBER REINFORCED ULTRA-HIGH-TEMPERATURE CERAMIC MATRIX COMPOSITES IN ARC-JET ENVIRONMENT

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Abstract

In the framework of the Horizon 2020 project C³HARME, an experimental campaign has been carried out to characterize a new class of Ultra-High-Temperature Ceramic Matrix Composites for near-zero ablation Aerospace Thermal Protection Systems. Small sized specimens, with ZrB₂-based matrix and different carbon fiber architectures, were exposed to a supersonic flow of simulated air generated by an arc-jet wind tunnel, achieving specific total enthalpies up to 20 MJ/kg, in an aero-thermo-chemical environment representative of atmospheric re-entry. Ablation rates were estimated by means of mass and thickness measurements before and after testing, demonstrating a good performance of the analyzed samples, although with some mechanical resistance issues. Surface temperatures were monitored by means of infrared pyrometers and a thermo-camera, and during most of the tests a spontaneous temperature jump was observed, with temperatures that reached values over 2800 K at the steady state. Computational Fluid Dynamics simulations allowed for the rebuilding of the thermo-fluid-dynamic and chemical flow field. Moreover, it was possible to propose a correlation of the temperature jump with an increased catalytic activity and a dramatic reduction of the thermal conductivity of the oxide layers forming on the exposed part of the sample, which anyway had a key role in preserving the unoxidized bulk materials at reasonable temperatures.

Keywords: Ultra-High-Temperature Ceramic Matrix Composites; Arc-jet wind tunnel testing; Near-zero ablation; Computational Fluid Dynamic simulation; Oxidation; Temperature Jump

Nomenclature

C	Specific heat capacity
D	Species diffusivity
H ₀	Specific total enthalpy
K	Catalytic recombination rate constant
k	Thermal conductivity
m	Molar mass
n	Normal direction
\dot{q}	Heat flux
R ₀	Universal gas constant
T	Temperature
t	Time
Y	Species concentration
γ	Catalytic recombination coefficient
ε	Emissivity
ρ	Density
σ	Stefan-Boltzmann constant

Subscripts

chem	Chemical
f	Fluid
int	Interface
rad	Radiative
s	Solid
w	Wall

Acronyms/Abbreviations

CEA	Chemical Equilibrium with Applications
CFD	Computational Fluid Dynamics
EDS	Energy Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy
HP	Hot Pressing
IR	Infrared
ISTEC	Institute of Science and Technology for Ceramics
SEM	Scanning Electron Microscopy
SPES	Small Planetary Entry Simulator
SPS	Spark Plasma Sintering
TC	Thermo-camera
TPS	Thermal Protection System
UHTC	Ultra-High-Temperature Ceramic
UHTCMC	Ultra-High-Temperature Ceramic Matrix Composite
UNINA	University of Naples “Federico II”

1. Introduction

Thermal Protection Systems (TPS) in hypersonic vehicles call for a unique combination of properties required to withstand the challenges of extremely demanding aero-thermo-dynamic conditions in harsh environments, including hypersonic Mach numbers, temperatures above 2000°C, the activation of gas

dissociation/recombination reactions at extremely low oxygen partial pressures, which can substantially enhance the heat flux on the exposed surface of the spacecraft [1,2].

Research efforts identified Ultra-High-Temperature Ceramics (UHTC) composites, based on transition metals carbides and diborides as potentially viable candidate systems for these applications, especially in light of their high melting temperatures, strength and oxidation resistance at temperatures over 2000°C [3,4]. The introduction of SiC or other silicon based ceramics as minority phase, in the form of particles, short fibers or whiskers [5-8], in the main refractory phase is frequently used to improve damage tolerance and oxidation resistance at intermediate temperature thanks to the formation of a borosilicate glass protective scale [9,10]. Due to the poor fracture toughness and thermal shock resistance of monolithic UHTC materials, research is currently oriented towards short and continuous Carbon Fiber reinforced Ultra-High-Temperature Ceramic Matrix Composites (UHTCMC), consisting of carbon fibers embedded in a UHTC-matrix [11], with the aim of developing large ultra-refractory components with enhanced mechanical properties and reliability for aerospace applications [12-17].

In this framework, University of Naples “Federico II” (UNINA) and the Institute of Science and Technology for Ceramics (ISTEC) are involved in the Horizon 2020 European C³HARME research project, focused on a new class of UHTCMCs for near zero-ablation thermal protection systems [18]. An extensive experimental characterization campaign is currently ongoing in the UNINA arc-jet wind tunnel, where atmospheric re-entry conditions are reproduced at maximum flow total enthalpies higher than 20 MJ/kg, supersonic Mach number and temperatures over 2000 °C in a gas atmosphere with high concentration of atomic oxygen. Non-intrusive diagnostic equipment, including two-color pyrometers and an infrared thermo-camera, is employed to monitor the surface temperature of the samples. Samples are analyzed after the exposition to the aero-thermo-chemically aggressive flow, with particular focus on the ablation rate.

The experimental activities are supported by Computational Fluid Dynamics simulations. Proper numerical models are defined, validated and employed to allow accurate prediction not only of the thermo-fluid-dynamic flow field around the test articles, but also of the thermal behavior of the materials samples, including an investigation of the effect of material properties, such as thermal conductivity and catalyticity.

2. Test setup and numerical models

2.1. Experimental setup

Experimental tests discussed in this paper were carried out in the arc-jet wind tunnel available at the

University of Naples “Federico II”, named SPES (Small Planetary Entry Simulator, Fig. 1). This is an open circuit, continuous blow-down wind tunnel where a nitrogen plasma can be generated by an industrial torch able to operate at powers up to 80 kW and mixed to a secondary cold oxygen flow in order to simulate earth atmospheric composition. A converging-diverging nozzle is employed to expand the hot mixture to a nominal supersonic Mach number equal to 3. A detailed facility description can be found in [19].

Fig. 1. SPES arc-jet wind tunnel available at UNINA.

Small sized material samples can be placed in front of nozzle exit section by a dedicated thermally protected supporting mechanism, in order to expose them to the supersonic dissociated air flow, and characterize materials response to the extreme aero-thermo-chemical environment. The nominal samples design for the present test campaign is displayed in Fig. 2. The UHTCMC samples were placed at a distance of 1 cm from nozzle exit.

Fig. 2 Nominal design of UHTCMC samples. Dimensions in mm.

The surface temperature of the samples was continuously measured ($\pm 1\%$ instrumental accuracy) by digital two-color pyrometers (Infratherm ISQ5 and IGAR6, Impac Electronic GmbH, Germany) at an acquisition rate of 100 Hz. In addition, an infrared (IR) thermo-camera (TC, Pyroview 512N, DIAS Infrared GmbH, Germany) allows for the evaluation of the temperature distribution over the sample surface. The ISQ5 pyrometer exploits two overlapping infrared wavelength bands at 0.7–1.15 μm and 0.97–1.15 μm to measure the actual temperature from 1273 K up to 3273 K. The IGAR6 pyrometer operates in the bands 1.5-1.6 μm and 2.0-2.5 μm to return the sample

temperature in the range 523-2273 K. The measurement area of the ISQ5 pyrometer is approximately a round spot 3.3 mm in diameter. The thermo-camera is able to detect temperature in the range 873-3273 K and it operates in the spectral range from 0.8 to 1.1 μm . The procedure employed to set the correct value of spectral emittance, on which the IR-TC measurement is dependent, is reported in [19]. High-Definition videos of the tests were recorded by means of a Camera Flea3 1.3 MP Color USB3 Vision with a resolution of 1328x1048 and a frame rate equal to 120 fps.

2.2. Test conditions

In the present test campaign, samples were exposed to a supersonic flow generated by the expansion of a high enthalpy gas mixture of Nitrogen (0.8 g/s) and Oxygen (0.2 g/s). During the test, the arc power of the plasma torch and consequently the total enthalpy of the flow are gradually increased through successive increments, leading correspondingly to an increase of pressure and temperature. A quasi-stationary condition generally occurs when the maximum value of temperature is reached during the last steps of the test. In the tests discussed in the present work, the nominal duration of each step was 30 seconds, except for the last step of 120 seconds. As shown below, preliminary tests had a shorter duration. The total specific enthalpy is obtained through an energy balance at the exit of the plasma torch, based on measurement of temperature and flow rate of cooling water [19]. In Table 1, the typical values of the physical quantities of interest for each torch arc power step are reported. Heat fluxes were measured by a copper slug calorimeter. The pressure in the test chamber was approximately equal to 2 mbar. Test conditions were consistent with the typical values obtained in previous experimental campaigns [20,21].

Table 1. Test conditions.

Step	H ₀ (MJ/kg)	Heat Flux - Slug Calorimeter (MW/m ²)	Stagnation Point Pressure (mbar)
0	5.5	0.8	62
1	7.0	0.95	64
2	8.5	1.1	67
3	10	1.5	70
4	12	2.0	73
5	14	2.5	76
6	16	3.0	79
7	18	3.6	82
8	20	4.2	85

2.3. Numerical models

In order to properly characterize the flow field inside the facility and to rebuild the thermal behavior of the samples, Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) simulations were performed.

A simplified 2D-axisymmetric computational domain, shown in Fig. 3(a), is employed to perform steady-state simulations of the high-enthalpy flow field inside the mixing chamber and supersonic nozzle. The Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes equations are solved for a turbulent multi-reacting gas mixture with five species (i.e. O, O₂, NO, N and N₂), in chemical non-equilibrium. Finite rate chemical reactions are considered, with the reaction rate constants specified by the Arrhenius law. Viscosity, thermal conductivity and mass diffusivities of the gas species are derived from the kinetic theory of gases. A density-based, steady, axisymmetric formulation of the equations is solved in these assumptions.

Through an axial mass flow inlet, representing the exit section of the torch, the specified mass flow rate of the hot gas (N₂, red in Fig. 3(a)) coming from the torch is injected into the domain. The gas total temperature and chemical composition are evaluated by means of the NASA CEA (Chemical Equilibrium with Applications) software [22] in order to match the total specific enthalpy corresponding to the desired value of the torch arc power. Furthermore, a radial mass flow inlet is used to simulate the injection of the cold gas (O₂, blue in Fig. 3(a)) in the mixing chamber.

The thermo-fluid-dynamic conditions achieved at the nozzle exit section, corresponding to the inlet section of the test chamber, are then used as inputs to study the aero-thermo-dynamic flow field around the test article. Axisymmetric steady-state simulations are performed on a computational domain which includes both the fluid region of the test chamber and the solid components (Fig. 3(b)). On the top and rear boundaries of the domain, a pressure-outlet condition corresponding to the experimental vacuum environment is set.

For the thermal analysis of the samples, the time-dependent temperature field inside the sample and its supporting elements can be computed solving the energy equation

$$(\rho C)_s \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = k_s \nabla^2 T \quad (1)$$

The distribution of the thermo-fluid dynamic quantities and the chemical compositions in the fluid area near the solid material, and subsequently the convective heat flux, are influenced by the temperature on the exposed surface of the sample. For these reasons, for an accurate approach the interaction between the fluid and the materials needs to be considered. The thermal coupling condition is set on the interfaces between fluid and solid domains, that is temperature and heat flux continuities:

$$T_{f,int} = T_{s,int} \quad (2)$$

$$k_f \frac{\partial T}{\partial n} \Big|_{f,int} + \dot{q}_{rad,in} + \dot{q}_{chem} = k_s \frac{\partial T}{\partial n} \Big|_{s,int} + \dot{q}_{rad,out} \quad (3)$$

where $\dot{q}_{rad,in}$ is the radiative heat flux entering the solid domain, \dot{q}_{chem} is the chemical contribution to the heat transfer (due to the dissociation/recombination reactions occurring at the solid/fluid interface),

$\dot{q}_{rad,out} = \varepsilon\sigma T^4$ is the radiative heat flux emitted by the solid surface.

Fig. 3. (a) Computational domain for arc-jet facility CFD simulations and b) computational domain for the simulation of the test chamber flow field and the thermal analysis of the samples.

2.3.1. Effect of the surface catalycity

Surface catalycity is defined as the ability of the material surface to promote exothermal recombination reactions at the wall. The diffusive flux of atomic species at the wall, part of which recombines into molecules, results in an increased heat flux, as shown in Eq. (3). According to [23], the diffusive flux at the wall for the i -th atomic species can be written as:

$$\frac{\partial Y_i}{\partial n} = \frac{Y_i K_w}{D_i} \quad (4)$$

where the material catalytic recombination rate constant K_w is both function of the wall material and on the considered chemical species. K_w can be expressed as function of the catalytic recombination coefficient γ_w :

$$K_w = \gamma_w \sqrt{\frac{R_0 T_w}{2\pi m_i}} \quad (5)$$

γ_w is the ratio between the number of atomic collisions effective in recombination and the total number of atomic collision occurring at the wall [24]. It can assume values between 0 and 1, being $\gamma_w = 0$ the case of not-catalytic wall (zero species diffusive flux) and $\gamma_w = 1$ the case of fully catalytic wall (zero atomic species concentration at the wall).

In the CFD simulation, it is possible to assign a specified value of the species concentration at the wall.

Extracting, from the fluid field solution, the quantities appearing in Eqs. (4) and (5), the values of K_w and γ_w can be calculated. In the present work, to reduce the number of unknown quantities, it has been assumed that the catalytic recombination coefficients are the same for the two atomic species, nitrogen and oxygen.

As discussed in section 4, it is important in this context to take into account surface catalycity since it has a primary influence on the material thermal behavior and equilibrium temperature.

3. Experimental results

3.1. Samples tested

A wide experimental campaign was carried out for the characterization of different formulations of UHTCMC materials. The present work focuses in particular on 8 samples, all based on a UHTC matrix with ZrB_2 as major component and SiC particles as minority phase. Different carbon fibers architectures have been compared: slurry infiltration followed by several overlapped plies with continuous fibers directions alternately arranged at 0° and 90° , and random dispersion of chopped fibers in the matrix.

Two samples with continuous coated fibers T800HB-PyC were manufactured, employing Hot Pressing (HP) as sintering process. One of them was

tested three times, at progressively increasing maximum enthalpy levels. Moreover, four XN80-XN60 chopped fibers samples (two sintered by Spark Plasma Sintering – SPS and two by HP) and two specimens with continuous uncoated XN80 fibers, sintered by HP, were manufactured.

Table 2 summarizes the most important information about all the samples tested, including their composition, the maximum temperature reached during the test, approximate test duration and the most relevant results obtained after exposure to a high-enthalpy hypersonic flow. Moreover, the Table shows the test conditions to which each sample was subjected, in terms of the enthalpy steps described in Table 1.

Samples surfaces were observed by a Digital Microscope KH-8700 (HIROX-USA, Inc., United States), employing a MX(G) 5040SZ optical lens with

50-400x magnification factor, before and after test, allowing to visualize the oxidation products, while a balance (1 mg accuracy) and a precision caliper (0.01 mm accuracy) were used to measure mass and thickness losses of the specimen. Erosion rates are calculated assuming as reference time the one spent by the specimen above 1500 K, because below this temperature the erosion is negligible, as demonstrated by the first preliminary test. In the post-processing analyses, two erosion rates were calculated: one based on the loss of mass (assuming uniform consumption of the sample in the axial direction) and the other evaluated by the thickness measurement made by the caliper. The average mass-based erosion rates are graphically represented in Fig. 4 and all of them are on the order of 10^{-3} - 10^{-4} mm/s. More details on the single tests are given in the following subsections.

Table 2. Main characteristics of the samples tested.

Sample ID	Carbon fibers	Matrix/ Fibers	Steps	T _{MAX} (K)	Duration (s)	Results/comments
HP-CLF-1	Continuous T800HB-PyC	50/50%	0	1435	250	Preliminary test
HP-CLF-1	Continuous T800HB-PyC	50/50%	1-5	2020	250	Reduced emissivity/ Negligible erosion
HP-CLF-1	Continuous T800HB-PyC	50/50%	1-8	2465	400	Surface delamination
HP-CLF-2	Continuous T800HB-PyC	50/50%	1-8	2480	400	Jump of radiance
SPS-SF-1	Chopped XN80	60/40%	2-8	2790	350	Temperature jump/ Zirconia scale detached
SPS-SF-2	Chopped XN60	60/40%	2-7	2720	400	Temperature jump/ Zirconia scale detached
HP-SF-1	Chopped XN60	60/40%	2-7	2685	400	Temperature jump/ Negligible erosion
HP-SF-2	Chopped XN60	60/40%	1-8	2850	400	Temperature jump/ Negligible erosion
HP-ULF-1	Continuous XN80	60/40%	2-7	2740	400	Temperature jump/ Negligible erosion
HP-ULF-2	Continuous XN80	60/40%	2-7	2700	400	Temperature jump/ Negligible erosion

Fig. 4. Erosion rates (mass-based) for the samples tested.

3.2. Test on continuous coated-fibers samples made by HP

As a preliminary test, sample HP-CLF-1 was exposed to a relatively low level of specific total enthalpy (step 0 of Table 1). It preserved perfectly its structural and functional integrity, so it was tested two more times, reaching enthalpy levels corresponding to steps 5 and 8. The maximum temperature reached was higher than 2400 K. After the last test, the sample head appeared completely oxidized, with the formation of a white ZrO_2 layer, and an evident delamination was observable in the outer layers (Fig. 6). An estimation of the spectral emissivity made by comparison of pyrometer and thermo-camera measurements revealed a progressive decrease in its value with increasing temperature, which appears to be coherent with existing literature [25,26].

Fig. 5. Temperature histories of samples HP-CLF-1 and HP-CLF-2.

However, an almost negligible erosion rate was detected, as reported in Table 3.

An interesting phenomenon was detected during test on HP-CLF-2, with the temperature measured by the thermo-camera suddenly experiencing a jump of over 200 K during the last enthalpy step, associated to the appearance of bubbles on the exposed face, possibly explainable by extrusion of volatile products through the liquid film of SiO_2 covering the surface (Fig. 7). The glassy phase was finally almost totally removed, leaving a zirconium dioxide layer exposed, according to the typical oxidation mechanism of ZrB_2 -10 vol% SiC ceramics [27]. The pyrometer did not detect any jumps, maybe because it was not directly pointed onto the localized instabilities, or due to the fact that this “jump-of-radiance” was associated to a reduction in spectral emissivity rather than to an actual temperature variation.

Both the samples showed a marked tendency of the external zirconia layer to spall-off after the exposition to the supersonic high-enthalpy flow.

Table 3. Ablation data for the three tests on sample HP-CLF-1.

Test number	1	2	3
Initial mass	4.781 g	4.777 g	4.763 g
Final mass	4.777 g	4.763 g	4.669 g
Average erosion rate (mass)	$2.3 \cdot 10^{-5}$ mm/s	$3.5 \cdot 10^{-4}$ mm/s	$4.9 \cdot 10^{-4}$ mm/s

Fig. 6. Pictures of HP-CLF-1 (a) before the tests, (b) after Test 1, (c) after Test 2, (d) after Test 3.

Fig. 7. Thermal images of surface instabilities on sample HP-CLF-2.

3.3. Test on chopped fibers samples made by SPS

Samples based on chopped fibers and sintered by SPS were tested reaching very high specific total enthalpy levels. The time history of the maximum surface temperature detected by the two-color pyrometer ISQ5 is shown in Fig. 8.

Fig. 8. Temperature histories of samples SPS-SF-1 and SPS-SF-2.

A temperature jump of several hundred degrees occurred for both the samples, when the temperature reached and exceeded about 2200 K. The phenomenon of temperature jump has been widely investigated in literature for SiC-containing UHTCs and C-SiC based ceramics [28], but still several interpretations are proposed, including: transition from passive to active oxidation of Silicon carbide [29,30]; triggering of catalytic recombination of Nitrogen atoms due to the presence of gaseous Silicon [31]; formation of cracks promoting Oxygen diffusion to inner SiC particles and carbon fibers, resulting in carbon exothermic oxidation and nitridation [30,32]; surface modifications altering properties of the samples such as emissivity and catalytic. All these factors could lead to completely different surface heat flows even under the same test conditions (same arc power, in the present case). As discussed in section 4, a possible interpretation based on a combination of increased catalytic efficiency and reduced thermal conductivity of the outer zirconia layer is here proposed, based on the outcomes of numerical simulations.

Furthermore, experimental tests showed the occurrence of instability phenomena in the form of bubbles nucleation (Fig. 9 (b)), explainable, as discussed in section 3.2, by extrusion of gaseous SiO, CO₂ or CO throughout the liquid film of silica formed on the surface at high temperature.

Fig. 9 Sample SPS-SF-1 (a) before, (b) during and (c) after instability.

Upon complete removal of SiO₂, a ZrO₂ layer with the characteristic white color appeared on the surface of both samples, but it demonstrated a poor adherence to the lower substrate, from which it detached. The thickness of this layer was about 0.45 mm and this phenomenon clearly affected the estimation of erosion rate, which is reported in Table 4.

Fig. 10. Sample SPS-SF-1 (a) before and (b) after the test with (c, d) detachment of a Zirconia layer.

Table 4. Mass and thickness data before and after the test for samples SPS-SF-1 and SPS-SF-2.

	SPS-SF-1	SPS-SF-2
Initial mass	6.788 g	6.235 g
Final mass	6.506 g	6.157 g
Average erosion rate (mass)	$1.1 \cdot 10^{-3}$ mm/s	$1.2 \cdot 10^{-3}$ mm/s
Initial thickness	5.09 mm	4.93 mm
Final thickness	4.89 mm	4.74 mm
Average erosion rate (thickness)	$0.71 \cdot 10^{-3}$ mm/s	$0.62 \cdot 10^{-3}$ mm/s

3.4. Test on chopped fibers samples made by HP

Samples HP-SF-1 and HP-SF-2 were tested reaching respectively enthalpy levels 7 and 8. In both cases, a temperature jump was detected by the pyrometer, with a maximum steady state temperature of over 2800 K (Fig. 11). However, despite the clearly noticeable signs of surface oxidation, evident in the comparison between Fig. 12(a) and (b), these samples preserved a perfect structural integrity, and showed an almost negligible erosion rate, based on mass measurements. It is interesting to observe that oxidation led to a thickening of samples heads, resulting in a negative ablation rate based on thickness measurement, as reported in the last row of Table 5.

Fig. 11. Temperature histories of samples HP-SF-1 and HP-SF-2.

Fig. 12. Sample HP-SF-2 (a) before and (b) after the test.

Table 5. Mass and thickness data before and after the test for samples HP-SF-1 and HP-SF-2.

	HP-SF-1	HP-SF-2
Initial mass	7.360 g	6.709 g
Final mass	7.270 g	6.553 g
Average erosion rate (mass)	$3.0 \cdot 10^{-4}$ mm/s	$5.6 \cdot 10^{-4}$ mm/s
Initial thickness	4.90 mm	5.01 mm
Final thickness	5.00 mm	5.05 mm
Average erosion rate (thickness)	$-3.2 \cdot 10^{-4}$ mm/s	$-1.3 \cdot 10^{-4}$ mm/s

3.5. Test on continuous uncoated-fibers samples made by HP

In this section, the results of tests performed on samples with uncoated continuous fibers and sintered by Hot Pressing are presented. Fig. 13 shows the thermal histories of the two samples as detected by the ISQ5 pyrometer. Also in this case during the last step a spontaneous rise in temperature to values between 2700 and 2800 K is observable.

A proper positioning of the IR thermo-camera allowed for a better visualization of the phenomenon of the temperature jump. Fig. 14(a) and (b) show the thermal distribution on sample HP-ULF-2 respectively just before and just after the jump. It appears clear that only the front part of the sample experiences a dramatic increase in temperature, whereas the rear body appears

to be almost unaffected by the jump. The temperature difference between the front surface and the rear region is testified also by the different brightness of the two regions, highlighted by the CCD picture taken during test on HP-SF-2, after the temperature jump, shown in Fig. 15.

Fig. 13. Temperature histories of samples HP-ULF-1 and HP-ULF-2.

Fig. 14. Thermal images of sample HP-ULF-2 (a) before and (b) after the temperature jump.

Fig. 15. CCD picture taken during test on HP-SF-2, after the temperature jump.

Also these samples showed a negligible erosion rate, preserving a perfect structural integrity after the exposition to the plasma jet (Fig. 16). The data related to mass and thickness variations for the two samples are reported in Table 6. Also in this case, an oxidation-

related thickening is highlighted by the negative erosion rate reported in the last row.

Fig. 16. Sample HP-ULF-1 (a) before and (b) after the test.

Table 6. Mass and thickness data before and after the test for samples HP-ULF-1 and HP-ULF-2.

	HP-ULF-1	HP-ULF-2
Initial mass	7.365 g	7.374 g
Final mass	7.265 g	7.300 g
Average erosion rate (mass)	$3.4 \cdot 10^{-4}$ mm/s	$2.5 \cdot 10^{-4}$ mm/s
Initial thickness	5.17 mm	4.98 mm
Final thickness	5.22 mm	5.01 mm
Average erosion rate (thickness)	$-1.7 \cdot 10^{-4}$ mm/s	$-1.0 \cdot 10^{-4}$ mm/s

4. Numerical simulations

Computational Fluid Dynamic simulations are employed to get more detailed information about the evolution of the aero-thermo-chemical flow field that develops in the facility and around the samples, and to provide possible interpretations for the thermal behavior of the materials.

In particular, the phenomenon of the temperature jump was preliminary investigated, selecting the last step of the test on HP-ULF-2 as a reference case. First, the thermo-fluid-dynamic and chemical field has been simulated, employing the numerical models described in section 2.3. Fig. 17 shows the Mach number and temperature distributions inside the mixing chamber and supersonic nozzle of the SPES wind tunnel, in the selected conditions ($H_0 = 18$ MJ/kg). The hot jet coming from the axial torch is clearly distinguishable.

The conditions obtained at the nozzle exit section were used as inputs for the simulation of the flow field around the test article. Fig. 18(a-d) show the distributions of pressure, temperature and mass fractions of dissociated oxygen and nitrogen. It is clear that the level of dissociation of molecular species is considerably high, condition that, as discussed below, results in a sensitive effect of surface catalycity on the heat fluxes.

Fig. 17. Distributions of (a) Mach Number and (b) static temperature inside mixing chamber and nozzle, conditions corresponding to Step 7 ($H_0 = 18$ MJ/kg).

Fig. 18. Distributions of (a) static pressure, (b) static temperature, (c) O mass fraction and (d) N mass fraction around the sample, conditions corresponding to Step 7 ($H_0 = 18$ MJ/kg).

The aero-thermo-chemical field was finally coupled to the thermal analysis of the sample, performing steady-state simulations to match the temperature distribution evaluated by the thermo-camera before and after the temperature jump. The sample density was set to 4000 kg/m^3 . The surface emissivity, based on an estimation made by comparison of pyrometer and

thermo-camera measurements, was set to 0.5. In order to match the temperature axial profile before the jump, the thermal conductivity was set to 40 W/m•K. Even before the occurrence of the temperature jump, a certain amount of catalytic recombination needed to be taken into account, with a catalytic efficiency $\gamma_w = 2 \cdot 10^{-2}$. To justify the sudden rise in temperature associated to the jump, and localized in the front part of the sample, as discussed in section 3.5, a double effect was considered, presumably related to the formation of a zirconia layer on the exposed surface, upon removal of SiO₂ glassy phase: an increase in catalytic activity ($\gamma_w = 1 \cdot 10^{-1}$) and a dramatic decrease in thermal conductivity in the oxidized region ($k = 2$ W/m•K, [33]). With these settings, and considering an oxide thickness of 800 μm , the experimental profile detected by the thermo-camera was rather well matched. The comparison between numerical and experimental temperature axial profiles is shown in Fig. 19.

Fig. 19. Comparison between numerical and experimental temperature axial profiles, before and after temperature jump, for sample HP-ULF-2.

A more detailed analysis of the phenomenon of the temperature jump is certainly required, also employing a deeper microstructural post-test characterization of the samples, based on Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) or Energy Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy (EDS). However, these preliminary results suggest that the formation of the zirconium oxide layer at ultra-high temperatures, besides promoting a dramatic increase in the surface temperature, on the other hand protects the unoxidized bulk material, whose temperature, as can be clearly seen in Fig. 19, does not exceed 2200 K even after the jump.

5. Conclusions

An extensive experimental campaign was carried out to characterize a new class of Ultra-High-Temperature Ceramic Matrix Composites based on ZrB₂-SiC matrix

and different carbon fibers architectures, in an environment representative of atmospheric re-entry. Small sized samples were exposed to a supersonic flow of simulated air in an arc-jet wind tunnel, at specific total enthalpies up to 20 MJ/kg and in presence of a considerable amount of dissociated oxygen. Most of the samples demonstrated an excellent ablation resistance, although some formulations revealed poor mechanical properties of the oxide phases forming after the exposition to the high-enthalpy flow. The surface temperature was monitored by non-intrusive infrared equipment, including two-color pyrometers and a thermo-camera. In most of the tests, a spontaneous temperature jump of several hundred degrees was observed even at fixed flow conditions, and temperatures over 2800 K were reached. The combined effort of experimental activities and numerical simulations allowed proposing an interpretation for the jump, based on a twofold mechanism, presumably related to the appearance of ZrO₂ on the external surface of the sample after complete removal of SiO₂ glassy phase: an increase in the catalytic activity and a strong reduction in thermal conductivity in the oxidized region. These results allow being confident on the good performance of the analyzed materials, which showed an excellent ablation resistance and the capability of the oxide phase to shelter the unoxidized material and keep it at acceptable temperatures. Further developments will include detailed micro-structural analyses to provide a deeper understanding of the observed phenomena, including the temperature jump, and the scale-up of the samples to more complex and larger geometries.

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References

- [1] W.G. Fahrenholtz, G.E. Hilmas, Ultra-high temperature ceramics: Materials for extreme environments, *Scripta Materialia* 129 (2017) 94-99.
- [2] E. Wuchina, E. Opila, M. Opeka, W. Fahrenholtz, I. Talmy, UHTCs: Ultra-High Temperature Ceramic materials for extreme environment applications, *Electrochem. Soc. Interface* 16 (2007) 30-36.

- [3] R. Savino, L. Criscuolo, G.D. Di Martino, S. Mungiguerra, Aero-thermo-chemical characterization of ultra-high-temperature ceramics for aerospace applications, *J. Eur. Ceram. Soc.* 38 (8) (2018) 2937-2953.
- [4] L. Silvestroni, H-J. Kleebe, W.G. Fahrenholtz, J. Watts Super-strong materials for temperatures exceeding 2000°C, *Sci. Rep.* 7 (2017), 40730, doi: 10.1038/srep40730.
- [5] L. Silvestroni, D. Sciti, Oxidation of ZrB₂ ceramics containing SiC as particles, whiskers, or short fibers, *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.* 94 (2011) 2796–2799. doi:10.1111/j.1551-2916.2011.04726.x.
- [6] A. Purwar, V. Thiruvengadam, B. Basu, Experimental and computational analysis of thermo-oxidative-structural stability of ZrB₂-SiC-Ti during arc-jet testing, *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.* 100 (10) (2017) 4860-4873.
- [7] P.J. Ritt, P.A. Williams, S.C. Splinter, J.H. Perepezko, Arc jet testing and evaluation of Mo-Si-B coated Mo and SiC-ZrB₂ ceramics, *J. Eur. Ceram. Soc.* 34 (15) (2014) 3521-3533.
- [8] F. Monteverde, D. Alfano, R. Savino, Effects of LaB₆ addition on arc-jet convectively heated SiC-containing ZrB₂-based ultra-high temperature ceramics in high enthalpy supersonic airflows, *Corros. Sci.* 75 (2013) 443-453.
- [9] E. P. Simonenko, D.V. Sevast'yanov, N.P. Simonenko, V.G. Sevast'yanov, N.T. Kuznetsov, Promising Ultra-High-Temperature Ceramic Materials for Aerospace Applications, *Rus. J. Inorg. Chem.* 58 (14) (2013) 1669–1693.
- [10] T.A. Parthasarathy, D. Petry, M.K. Cinibulk, T. Mathur, M.R. Mark, R. Gruber, Thermal and Oxidation Response of UHTC Leading Edge Samples Exposed to Simulated Hypersonic Flight Conditions, *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.* 96 (3) (2013) 907-915.
- [11] S. Tang, C. Hu, Design, Preparation and Properties of Carbon Fiber Reinforced Ultra-High Temperature Ceramic Composites for Aerospace Applications: A Review, *J. Mater. Sci. Technol.* 33 (2) (2017) 117-130, doi: 10.1016/j.jmst.2016.08.004.
- [12] L. Zoli, D. Sciti, Efficacy of a ZrB₂-SiC matrix in protecting C fibres from oxidation in novel UHTCMC materials, *Materials & Design.* 113 (2017) 207–213. doi:10.1016/j.matdes.2016.09.104.
- [13] A. Vinci, L. Zoli, D. Sciti, M. Cesare, S. Guicciardi, Understanding the mechanical properties of novel UHTCMCs through random forest and regression tree analysis, *Mater. Des.* 145 (2018) 97–107. doi:10.1016/j.matdes.2018.02.061.
- [14] A. Vinci, L. Zoli, E. Landi, D. Sciti, Oxidation behaviour of a continuous carbon fibre reinforced ZrB₂-SiC composite, *Corros. Sci.* 123 (2017) 129-138. doi:10.1016/j.corsci.2017.04.012.
- [15] L. Zoli, A. Vinci, P. Galizia, C. Melandri, D. Sciti, On the thermal shock resistance and mechanical properties of novel unidirectional UHTCMCs for extreme environments, *Sci. Rep.* Submitted (2018).
- [16] P. Galizia, S. Failla, L. Zoli, D. Sciti, Tough salami-inspired C_f/ZrB₂UHTCMCs produced by electrophoretic deposition, *J. Eur. Ceram. Soc.* 38 (2018). doi:10.1016/j.jeurceramsoc.2017.09.047.
- [17] L. Silvestroni, D. Dalle Fabbriche, C. Melandri, D. Sciti, Relationships between carbon fiber type and interfacial domain in ZrB₂-based ceramics, *J. Eur. Ceram. Soc.* 36 (2016) 17–24. doi:10.1016/j.jeurceramsoc.2015.09.026.
- [18] C³HARME Project Website: <https://c3harme.eu/>.
- [19] F. Monteverde, A. Cecere, R. Savino, Thermo-chemical surface instabilities of SiC-ZrB₂ ceramics in high enthalpy dissociated supersonic air flows, *J. Eur. Ceram. Soc.* 37 (6) (2017) 2325-2341.
- [20] A. Cecere, R. Savino, C. Allouis, F. Monteverde, Heat transfer in ultra-high temperature advanced ceramics under high enthalpy arc-jet conditions, *Int. J. Heat Mass Transf.* 91 (2015) 747-755.
- [21] F. Monteverde, D. Alfano, R. Savino, Effects of LaB₆ addition on arc-jet convectively heated SiC-containing ZrB₂-based ultra-high temperature ceramics in high enthalpy supersonic airflows, *Corros. Sci.* 75 (2013) 443-453.
- [22] S. Gordon, B.J. McBride, Computer Program of Complex Chemical Equilibrium Compositions and Applications, NASA Reference Publication 1311, 1994.
- [23] O.N. Suslov, G.A. Tirskiy, The kinetics of the recombination of nitrogen atoms on high temperature reusable surface insulation in hypersonic thermo-chemical non-equilibrium flow, 2nd European Symposium on Aerothermodynamics for Space Vehicles, Noordwijk, The Netherlands, November 1994 (ESA SP-367, February 1995).
- [24] S.M. Scala, Hypersonic Heat Transfer to Catalytic Surfaces, Ramo-Wooldridge Second Symposium on Ballistic Missiles, Los Angeles, California, June 1957.
- [25] Y.S. Touloukian, D.P. DeWitt, Thermophysical properties of matter – The TPRC Data Series, Vol. 8, Thermal radiative properties: nonmetallic solids, IFI/Plenum, New York – Washington, 1972.
- [26] G.T. Van Laningham, Oxidation resistance, thermal conductivity, and spectral emittance of fully dense zirconium diboride with silicon carbide and tantalum diboride additives, PhD Thesis, Georgia Institute of Technology, May 2012.
- [27] T.A. Parthasarathy, R.A. Rapp, M. Opeka, M.K. Cinibulk, Modeling Oxidation Kinetics of SiC-Containing Refractory Diborides, *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.* 95 (1) (2012), 338-349.

- [28] J. Marschall, D. Pejakovic, W.G. Fahrenholtz, G.E. Hilmas, F. Panerai, O. Chazot. Temperature Jump Phenomenon During Plasmatron Testing of ZrB₂-SiC Ultrahigh-Temperature Ceramics, *J. Thermoph. Heat Transf.* 26 (4) (2012) 559-572.
- [29] I. Sakraker, C.O. Asma, Experimental investigation of passive/active oxidation behavior of SiC based ceramic thermal protection materials exposed to high enthalpy plasma, *J. Eur. Ceram. Soc.* 33 (2013) 351-359.
- [30] M. Balat-Pichelin, L. Charpentier, F. Panerai, O. Chazot, B. Helber, K. G. Nickel, Passive/active oxidation transition for CMC structural materials designed for the IXV vehicle reentry phase, *J. Eur. Ceram. Soc.* 35 (2) (2015) 487-502.
- [31] H. Hald, Operational limits for reusable space transportation systems due to physical boundaries of C/SiC materials, *Aerosp. Sci. Technol.* 7 (7) (2003) 551-559.
- [32] G. Herdrich, M. Fertig, S. Löhle, S. Pidan, M. Auweter-Kurtz, T. Laux, Oxidation behavior of Silicon carbide-based materials by using new probe techniques, *J. Spacecr. Rocket* 42 (5) (2015) 817-824.
- [33] K.W. Schlichting, N.P. Padture, P.G. Klemens, Thermal conductivity of dense and porous yttria-stabilized zirconia, *J. Mater. Sci.* 36 (2001) 3003-3010.